

EOSC ASSOCIATION
Task Force Financial Sustainability
2023
SURVEY

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

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Introduction

In November 2022, the Task Force Financial Sustainability published its [progress report](#) that summarises the results of a year of discussions and research on how the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) can progress towards becoming financially sustainable. The Task Force is now interested in gathering feedback from the EOSC community, including the EOSC Tripartite Governance, EOSC Association mandated organisations and Task Forces, and relevant experts involved in EOSC projects, ESFRI RIs and clusters, and European e-Infrastructures. The Task Force will use this feedback to evaluate its proposals and recommendations, and inform the possible direction of its second year of activity.

We expect respondents to be familiar with the content of the progress report. References to the specific sections are included in the survey where appropriate.

Privacy policy

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I accept the privacy policy

Funding models for the EOSC Core

1: To what extent do you agree with the initial proposal made for funding the EOSC Core? (Cf. [TF FinSust Progress Report](#), Section 3, p. 20-23)

- Strongly agree
- Somewhat agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Somewhat disagree
- Strongly disagree

2: If you disagree with the initial proposal, please substantiate your answer (max 500 characters)

500 character(s) maximum

3: What do you consider to be the critical success factors for funding the EOSC Core? (max 500 characters)

500 character(s) maximum

Funding models for the EOSC Exchange

4: Do you agree that the main role of the Exchange is to facilitate service findability service transactions and cost recovery mechanisms? (Cf. [TF FinSust Progress Report](#), Section 4.3, p. 28)

- Strongly agree
- Somewhat agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Somewhat disagree
- Strongly disagree

5: If you disagree, please substantiate your answer (max 500 characters)

500 character(s) maximum

6: Referring to section 4.1 Centrally Financed Services in the report, do you agree that services and resources deemed essential to conduct research should be centrally funded? (Cf. [TF FinSust Progress Report](#), Section 4.1, p. 25-26)

- Strongly agree
- Somewhat agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Somewhat disagree
- Strongly disagree

7: If you disagree, please substantiate your answer (max 500 characters)

500 character(s) maximum

8: Do you agree that the Exchange should maintain a limited portfolio of procurement-compliant agreements with commercial service providers to facilitate access to services? (Cf. [TF FinSust Progress Report](#), Section 4.2, p. 26-28)

- Strongly agree
- Somewhat agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Somewhat disagree
- Strongly disagree

9: If you disagree, please substantiate your answer (max 500 characters)

500 character(s) maximum

10: In the Progress Report, several possible payment mechanisms for brokered services in the EOSC Exchange are mentioned (cf. [TF FinSust Progress Report](#), Section 4.3.1, pp. 28-29). Please indicate how important you believe each of the following mechanisms to be for EOSC.

	very important	somewhat important	neither important nor unimportant	not very important	not at all important
Virtual access	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Voucher /token	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Direct payment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Subscription	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Freemium	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

11: If you think any of these mechanisms is not important, please explain why? (max 500 characters)

500 character(s) maximum

12: If there are other mechanisms not mentioned in the above list which you think it is important to consider, please describe them and explain why they are important (max 500 characters)

500 character(s) maximum

13: In your opinion, what are the essential elements to guarantee the financial sustainability of the EOSC Exchange? (max 500 characters)

500 character(s) maximum

14: Do you agree with the description that the EOSC Data Federation should be designed to enable researchers to find and acquire data from multiple sources available at any of the levels of aggregation (local/institutional, national, thematic, European or international) through attribute-based discovery (Cf. [TF FinSust Progress Report](#), Section 2.3 of the progress report, p.18-19)

- Strongly agree
- Somewhat agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Somewhat disagree
- Strongly disagree

15: If you disagree, please explain what should be removed or is missing from this description (max 500 characters)

500 character(s) maximum

16: In your opinion, what are the essential elements to ensure the financial sustainability of the EOSC Data Federation? (max 500 characters)

500 character(s) maximum

17: The interoperability of data catalogues is an essential requirement for the EOSC to deliver its expected added value. Below we include the different additional costs identified by the Task Force to achieve interoperability (Cf. [TF FinSust Progress Report](#), Section 5.4.2 on p.38-39). The responsibility for performing these activities among the various “levels of aggregation” within the research landscape (i.e. institutional/local, national, thematic/disciplinary, EU, international/global), however, is currently not clearly allocated. Please select which levels should, in your opinion, bear the costs for the different cost categories.

	institutional /local	national	thematic /disciplinary	EU	international /global
Operational Costs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Development costs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Costs related to converting legacy data into FAIR data	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Storage and archival costs for sustainable repositories	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Costs to update metadata and APIs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Costs to connect endpoints and make data findable via data catalogues across Europe	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cost of all tools and services for making data FAIR	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Development of workflows and software	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Development of data analysis environments	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Development and maintenance of software catalogues	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Development and maintenance of computing capacity to run data analysis	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Development and maintenance of data transfer protocols	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Creating links and enabling interoperability between data resources and EOSC	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Operational costs related to federating interoperable data in EOSC	<input type="checkbox"/>				

18: If there are in your opinion additional costs which have not been identified in section 5.4.2, please indicate them here (max 500 characters)

500 character(s) maximum

19: Please indicate up to three (3) cost categories or sub-categories related to the EOSC Data Federation on which the TF FinSust should focus.

	Cost categories or sub-categories
1	
2	
3	

20: Referring to your answer to the previous question, please indicate any considerations that are relevant in your opinion for the long-term funding of these cost (sub-)categories

500 character(s) maximum

General

21: Please indicate any aspects relevant for the financial sustainability of EOSC that in your opinion are not sufficiently covered, or have not been considered in the progress report.

500 character(s) maximum

Demographics

* Name

* Position

* Organisation

* Your answer represents the opinion of:

- yourself
- an EOSC-A Task Force*
- an EOSC-A mandated organisation
- an EOSC project*
- a MS/AC*
- a Research Infrastructure*
- a cluster*
- an e-Infrastructure*

other

* please, specify:

* Are you available to be contacted if we have further questions related to your answers to this consultation?

Yes

No

* Please provide us with your email:

Data Protection information

* The Task Force may be interested in share publicly some of the responses and comments obtained. Published responses would be anonymous, with only the stakeholder category associated with them. Please indicate your preference by ticking the appropriate box below.

Yes, I agree with my responses to be shared publicly preserving anonymity.

No, I prefer that my responses are not shared publicly.

End

We thank you for completing the survey. Feedback from the EOSC community is much needed to help the EOSC Task Force on Financial Sustainability fine-tune its approach towards this very crucial question for the future of EOSC!

You have almost completed the survey,

please continue and submit responses,

or go back to make changes.

Once you proceed, it will not be possible to further modify your responses.

